

doi 10.5281/zenodo.7474022

Vol. 05 Issue 12 Dec - 2022

Manuscript ID: #0762

THE INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEE WORK DISCIPLINE AT THE EDUCATION OFFICE OF SAMARINDA CITY

Maskan, AF¹, Ahmad Jubaidi², Jamiah³ and Fitriyani⁴

^{1,2&3}Lecturer in the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences University of 17 August 1945 Samarinda

⁴Student in the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences University of 17 August 1945 Samarinda

*Corresponding author: *Ahmad Jubaidi*
Email: jubaidiahmad@yahoo.co.id

ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to find out how the influence of leadership on employee work discipline at the Office of the Education Personnel Office in Samarinda City.

The research was conducted at the Office of the Education and Culture Office of Samarinda City. This research used a correlational method and a quantitative approach.

In this study, the population was the City of Samarinda Education and Culture Office employees, totaling 66 people and the sample in this study was 40 people. There are 2 ways to collect data, namely: (1) field studies through observation, interviews and questionnaires/questions. and (2) literature study.

Data analysis was carried out, namely: (1) test the validity of the research instrument; (2) test the reliability of the research instrument, (3) simple linear regression analysis, then to test the truth of the research hypothesis using the t test, (4) the correlation coefficient and (5) the coefficient of determination. All data processing uses the Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) 25.0 software program.

The results of the study show that: (1) there is a positive influence between leadership variables on work discipline variables; and the value of the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) = 0.423, which means that the influence of the leadership variable on the work discipline variable is 42.30%. (2) The coefficient value of the leadership variable is 0.499 which means that if the leadership variable (X) is increased by 1 unit, the employee's work discipline will increase by 0.499; and (3) the coefficient of the leadership variable is positive, which means that the better the existing leadership, the employee work discipline will increase.

KEYWORDS:

Leadership and Work Discipline.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is one of the issues in management that is still interesting enough to be discussed today. The mass media, both electronic and print, often displays opinions and talks that discuss leadership. The role of a leader is very strategic and important for achieving the vision, mission and goals of an organization.

In this case the leader in an agency must be able to actually move and direct its employees, so that later it does not create obstacles in the process of administering government in an office as the highest leader, the leader has the obligation and authority to mobilize and provide direction to his subordinates so that they can provide services. the best for the community, one of which is by increasing the work discipline of employees so that in carrying out their duties they do so sincerely, willingly, and enthusiastically and have a sense of responsibility for their duties and are efficient and effective in achieving a common goal.

Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning the State Civil Apparatus (ASN), states that "Civil Servants are positioned as executors of public policy, public servants, glue and unifier of the nation. Civil Servants carry out policies set by the leadership of government agencies. In carrying out their duties , Civil Servants must be free from the influence and intervention of all groups and political parties. And in Law Number 5 of 2014, it also provides a guarantee of position and legal certainty for Civil Servants to organize and compile clean and authoritative apparatus. Development and refinement as well as the utilization of government apparatus, both institutionally and administratively in terms of staffing need to be continuously improved to achieve development as a whole.

Due to their important position and role, civil servants are always required to have loyalty and obedience as well as full discipline in carrying out their duties by focusing attention and thoughts and directing all their power and energy in an efficient and effective manner.

Civil Servant Development is aimed at being able to have full loyalty and obedience in carrying out the Government's duties and as an appreciation for this demand the Government issues a Government Regulation concerning Civil Servant Discipline Regulations Number 94 of 2021. This regulation contains main obligations, prohibitions and sanctions if obligations are not obeyed or violated by Civil Servants but on the contrary a civil servant who has fulfilled or complied with the principles contained in the apparatus can be said to have discipline. Therefore, it can be said that the most important element in improving the quality of the State Apparatus is by increasing the work discipline of the State Apparatuses in carrying out their duties.

According to Siagian (2014) discipline is management action to encourage members of the organization to fulfill the demands of these various provisions. Hasibuan (2018) stated that work discipline is a person's ability to work regularly, diligently continuously and work in accordance with applicable rules by not violating predetermined rules. Discipline is defined if employees always come and go home on time, do all tasks properly and correctly, comply with all company regulations and applicable social norms. Discipline must be enforced in an organization/company. Because without the support of good employee discipline, it will be difficult for the company to realize its goals. Furthermore, stated by Martoyo (2007) that there are several factors that influence employee work discipline, including: motivation, education and training, leadership, welfare and enforcement of discipline. Then stated by Dharma (2001) that leadership style, motivation, effective communication, the existence of regulations, rewards and compensation are factors that influence work discipline.

Therefore, discipline must be possessed by every government apparatus, both at the central level and those at the lower levels. Discipline owned by a government service office which is expected to support each other in improving national discipline which is directly related to duties and obligations to be able to create cooperation and service to the community as the main task of Government.

Discipline development for Civil Servants in an office or government agency is not as easy as imagined, employees have different behaviors so that in the implementation of work as their main tasks and functions sometimes experience non-uniformity of steps, movements and unity of views among employees which ultimately affects work and percentage employee work.

The Education Office is a government agency that plays a role in developing, improving quality and coordinating elements of education. It is in this institution that the activities of employees are expected to be able to play a role in realizing an educational pattern and be able to overcome all problems related to the quality of education. The Office of the Samarinda City Education Office is one of the educational institutions at the regional level of Samarinda City which is responsible for developing, improving the quality and coordinating elements of education within the city of Samarinda. It is in this agency or institution that the employees of the Samarinda City Education Office should work optimally for the advancement of the quality of education at the Samarinda city level.

The aim of the study was to find out how leadership influences employee work discipline at the Office of the Education Personnel Office in Samarinda City.

THEORITICAL REVIEW

According to Kartono (2005) that a leader is a person who has skills and strengths, especially skills in one area, so that he is able to influence other people to jointly carry out certain activities, for the achievement of one or several goals.

According to Berman Sihite et al (2020) that leadership is an activity of directing employees to realize predetermined goals, encouraging employees to follow the leadership's directions in realizing organizational goals, motivating employees to change the service culture in a better direction. Furthermore, it was stated by Suhudi et al (2018) that a good leader is a leader who can provide justice for his employees without favoritism, always gives suggestions to his employees, can appreciate the achievements of his employees, becomes a source of inspiration for his employees in solving problems that exist within the organization.

According to Siagian (2014), the role of leadership is influenced by factors which are also indicators of leadership, namely: communication, direction and guidance; motivating, rewarding. Then according to Singodimejo in Sutrisno (2009) states that discipline is an attitude of willingness and willingness of a person to obey and obey the norms of regulations that apply around him.

The work discipline is influenced by factors which are also indicators of work discipline by Soejono (2006), namely:

1. *Timeliness*

Timeliness here is defined as an attitude or behavior that shows adherence to working hours which includes: attendance and compliance of employees during working hours, employees carrying out their duties in a timely manner and correctly having the ability to deal with the work that is their responsibility as an employee. Who always completes the tasks assigned to him in accordance with procedures and is responsible for the results of his work.

2. *Loyalty/Compliance with the Rules*

Written and unwritten rules and regulations are made so that the goals of an organization can be achieved properly. For this reason, an employee's loyalty to the commitments that has been set is required. Loyalty here means obedience and obedience in carrying out orders from superiors and rules, regulations have been established. As well as the obedience of employees in wearing office uniforms, using identity cards, making permits when not entering the office, is also a reflection of high discipline.

3. *Responsibility in doing the task*

There are not a few employees who often find excuses for not completing their responsibilities so if you find employees like this, they can hinder the company from developing and moving forward. Therefore, an employee must have responsibility for every task that has been given to him.

One of the factors in realizing work discipline in employees can be done through the attitudes and behavior of leaders, continuous supervision, job satisfaction, motivation, work environment and other facilities and infrastructure (Rahmi et al. 2020). According to Bugdol (2018) that work discipline is the main basis for realizing sincerity at work, fulfilling working time and compliance with the norms that apply in an organization.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research was conducted at the Office of the Education and Culture Office of Samarinda City. This research used a correlational method and a quantitative approach.

In this study, the population consisted of 66 employees of the City of Samarinda Education and Culture Office and the sample in this study was 40 people. The sample was taken using the Solvin formula at a significant level of 10%.

There are 2 ways to collect data, namely: (1) field studies through observation, interviews and questionnaires/questions. The questionnaire in this study refers to the Likert scale with answers categorized as attitude questions as follows: strongly agree answers are given a value of 5, agree answers are given a value of 4, doubtful answers are given a value of 3, disagree answers are given a value of 2, and answers strongly disagree agree is given a value of 1; and (2) literature study is the collection of secondary data obtained from books, previous research journals, and other sources such as magazines, articles, newspapers, and others.

Data analysis was carried out, namely: (1) test the validity of the research instrument; (2) test the reliability of the research instrument, (3) simple linear regression analysis, then to test the truth of the research hypothesis using the t test, (4) the correlation coefficient and (5) the coefficient of

determination. All data processing using the Statistics Product and Service Solution (SPSS) software program 25.0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Data analysis

1. Research Instrument Validity Test

The validity of the research instrument is to measure the accuracy of the data that has been collected. The results of the validity test of the leadership variable (X) are presented in Table 1 and the results of the validity test of the work discipline variable (Y) are presented in Table 2.

Table1. Leadership Variable Validity Test Results

Variable	Item	Pearson Correlation (r-count)	Sig (2-tailed)	(r-table)	Validity Status
Communication	X1	0.822	0.000	0.312	VALID
	X2	0.767	0.000	0.312	VALID
Directions and Guidance	X3	0.523	0.001	0.312	VALID
	X4	0.623	0.000	0.312	VALID
Supervision	X5	0.707	0.000	0.312	VALID
	X6	0.692	0,000	0.312	VALID
Motivating	X7	0.765	0.000	0.312	VALID
	X8	0.624	0.000	0.312	VALID

Table 2. Work Discipline Variable Validity Test Results (Y)

Variable	Item	Pearson Correlation (r-count)	Sig (2-tailed)	(r-table)	Validity Status
Punctuality	Y1	0.575	0.000	0.312	VALID
	Y1	0.654	0.000	0.312	VALID
Loyalty / Compliance with the Rules	Y2	0.880	0.000	0.312	VALID
	Y2	0.867	0.000	0.312	VALID
Responsibility	Y3	0.763	0.000	0.312	VALID
	Y3	0.587	0.000	0.312	VALID

Based on the results of the data validity test in Table 1 and Table 2, it shows that all questions for the independent variable of leadership (X) and the dependent variable of work discipline (Y) are declared valid, that is, all r counts > r tables (0.312). So the data used is valid.

2. Research Instrument Reliability Test

The reliability test was used to measure whether the questionnaire used would produce the same measurement when used at different times and places. A variable is said to be reliable if it gives a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60, whereas if it is below 0.60 the data is said to be unreliable. If the alpha is close to one, then the reliability of the data is more reliable (Ghozali, 2009). The results of the reliability test of the leadership variable (X) are presented in Table 3. And the results of the reliability test of the work discipline variable (Y) are presented in Table 4.

Table 3. Leadership Variable Reliability Test Results (X)**Item-Total Statistics**

Variable	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
X1	29.38	17.522	.735	.805
X2	29.33	18.122	.660	.816
X3	29.18	21.687	.410	.845
X4	29.03	21.256	.535	.834
X5	29.28	19.333	.599	.825
X6	29.43	18.815	.559	.831
X7	29.38	18.702	.671	.815
X8	29.53	19.948	.490	.838

Table 4. Work Discipline Variable Reliability Test Results (Y)**Item-Total Statistics**

Variable	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Y1	21.13	11.907	.423	.824
Y2	21.23	11.307	.511	.809
Y3	21.23	9.204	.802	.743
Y4	21.58	8.456	.755	.754
Y5	21.20	10.626	.652	.782
Y6	21.15	11.567	.415	.827

Recapitulation of the reliability test results of the leadership variable (Y) and work discipline variable (Y) is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

No.	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Remark
1.	Leadership	0.845	Reliabel
2.	Work Discipline	0.822	Reliabel

Based on Tables 3, 4 and 5 the reliability test results show that the independent variable leadership (X) with Cronbach's Alpha value = 0.845 > 0.60 and the dependent variable work discipline (Y) with Cronbach's Alpha value = 0.822 > 0.60, it can be said that the data used reliable/reliable.

B. Hypothesis Testing

1. Simple Linear Regression

The results of a simple linear regression analysis to determine the effect of the independent variable leadership (X) on the dependent variable of work discipline (Y) are presented in Table 6. based on the table of values in the distribution with a total sample of 40, the value of t-table = 2.021.

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	8.785	3.202		2.743	.009
Leadership	.499	.095	.650	5.276	.000

Based on Table 6 above it is known that the Constant value (a) = 8,785 and the value of work discipline (b/regression coefficient) = 0.499, so that a simple linear regression equation is obtained as follows:

$$Y = 8,785 + 0,499X$$

Based on the simple linear regression equation above, it can be stated that: (1) the constant is 8.785, which means that when leadership (X) is ignored or zero, the work discipline is 8.785; (2) the coefficient of the leadership variable is 0.499 which means that if the leadership variable (X) is increased by 1 unit, the employee's work discipline will increase by 0.499; (3) the coefficient of the leadership variable is positive, which means that the better the existing leadership, the employee's work discipline will increase.

Based on table 6 above, it shows that significant value = 0.000 < 0.05, t-count = 5.276 > t-table = 2.021, so it can be stated that there is a significant influence between the leadership variable (X) on the work discipline variable (Y).

2. Correlation Coefficient and Coefficient of Determination

To determine the closeness of the relationship between leadership variables and work discipline variables, the correlation coefficient (r) is used and to determine the magnitude of the influence of leadership variables on work discipline, the coefficient of determination is used (R²). The results of data analysis are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Correlation Coefficient Value and Determination Coefficient
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.650 ^a	.423	.408	2.942

Based on the results of the analysis presented in Table 7, it shows that the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.650, which means that the relationship between the leadership variable (X) and the work discipline variable (Y) is 0.650 (classified as strong); The coefficient of determination is 0.423,

which means that the influence of the dependent variable (X) on the work discipline variable (Y) is 0.423 (42.30%), while 0.477 (47.70%) is influenced by other variables outside the leadership variable.

B. Discussion

Based on the results of the analysis that has been done, it shows that employee work discipline is influenced by the attitude and behavior of the leadership. The attitude and behavior of the leadership in question is a fair attitude towards all employees regardless of employee background or family relations (Mulyani et al, 2019). Actions in providing a sense of fairness to employees must be accompanied by concrete actions, meaning that a leader's actions must be in line with what he says (Loan et al, 2020). A good leader is a leader who cares about his employees, is able to facilitate his employees in realizing agency goals. The attitude of a fair leader will have an impact on eliminating egocentricity among employees and employees will not feel burdened in carrying out their work. As stated by Manley and Titchen (2017) that a catalytic leader is a leader who is able to increase the resources of his employees and position his employees according to their competencies.

Employee work discipline can be increased if leaders in carrying out supervision do not just find fault with employees, but become agents of change (Kalliola and Mahlakaarto, 2020). Work discipline will increase if leaders can understand the needs of their employees and are sensitive to change. If the leader already understands what are the strengths and weaknesses of employees, then this can be used as a guide in improving agency performance, so that what is the vision, mission and goals of the agency can be achieved (Stinglhamber et al, 2021).

The obstacle that often occurs in an agency/organization is not achieving a job effectively and efficiently as a result of not having good cooperation between leaders and supervisors and also between fellow employees. For this reason, leaders must be sensitive to issues that hinder the achievement of agency goals, and always pay attention to employees in completing their duties and responsibilities, and fostering good cooperation.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research reported by Nasution and Ichsan (2021) that leadership has a significant effect on employee work discipline at the Karo District Education Office; The results of other studies reported by Mendrofa et al (2021) show that leadership variables have a positive effect on employee work discipline.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTION

A. Conclusion

Based on data analysis and discussion it can be concluded as follows:

1. Based on the hypothesis test that the result is $t \text{ count} = 5.276 > r \text{ table} = 2.021$. So it can be concluded that there is a positive influence between leadership variables on work discipline variables; and the value of the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) = 0.423, which means that the influence of the leadership variable on the work discipline variable is 42.30%, while the remaining 47.70% is influenced by other variables.
2. The constant value is 8.785, which means that when leadership (X) is ignored or zero, work discipline is 8.785 and the leadership variable coefficient is 0.499, which means that if the leadership variable (X) is increased by 1 unit, employee work discipline will increase by 0.499.
3. The coefficient of the leadership variable is positive, which means that the better the existing leadership, the employee work discipline will increase.

B. Suggestion

1. For the Samarinda City Education Office, it is hoped that the Head of Service can pay more attention to factors that affect the increase and decrease in employee work discipline which can be seen from the aspects of direction and guidance and supervision by providing direction and guidance and supervising the work of employees who can assess and correct the implementation of tasks his employees. This is done in order to create better work discipline for its employees.
2. Employees of the Samarinda City Education Office are expected to further increase their sense of responsibility in carrying out a job with a commitment to carry out the work that has been given by their leaders, completing work on their own initiative without having to be ordered to achieve the vision and mission of the Samarinda City Education Office, because with an increase in work discipline can be more productive and more operational in the completion of each job.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Berman, S. O., Andika, C. B., & Prasetya, A. B. (2020). A Literature Review: Does Transformational Leadership impact and Effective in the Public Bureaucratic. *International Journal of Sociology, Policy and Law (IJOSPL)*, 01(01), 44–50. <http://www.ijospl.org>
- Bugdol, M. (2018). *A Different Approach to Work Discipline: Models, Manifestations and Methods of Behaviour Modification*. Switzerland: AG part of Springer Nature.
- Dharma, A. 2001. *Supervision Management*. Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta.
- Ghozali, I. 2009. *Mutivariate Analysis Application with IBM SPSS 19 Program*. BP Undip, Semarang.
- Hasibuan, S. M., and Bahri, S. 2018. The Influence of Leadership, Work Environment and Work Motivation on Performance. *Maneggio: Scientific Journal of Master of Management*, 1(1), 71–80.
- Kalliola, S., & Mahlakaarto, S. (2020). Methods of Promoting Professional Agency at Work. *Challenges*, 11(2), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/challe11020030>
- Kartono. 2005. *Leaders and Leadership*. Jakarta: Rajawali.
- Loan, L. T. M. (2020). The Influence of Organizational Commitment on Employees' Job Performance: The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction. *Management Science Letters*, 10(14), 3307–3312. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.6.007>
- Manley, K., & Titchen, A. (2017). Manley, K., & Titchen, A. (2017). Facilitation Skills: The Catalyst For Increased Effectiveness in Consultant Practice and Clinical Systems Leadership. *Educational Action Research*, 25(2), 256–279. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09650792.2016.1158118>
- Martoyo, S. 2007. *Human Resource Management*. BPEE, Yogyakarta.
- Mendfora, S.A.; Syahyarand B.K. Fawzee. 20210. The Influence of Leadership, Supervision and Job Satisfaction on Employee Work Discipline. *Alignment Journal* 4 (2) : 130 – 140
- Mulyani, S. R., Sari, V. N., & Sari, M. W. (2019). The Model of Employee Motivation and Cooperative Employee Performance. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 20(2), 379–390. <https://doi.org/10.17512/pjms.2019.20.2.32>
- Nasution, L. and R.N. Ichsan. 2021. The Effect of Leadership Implementation on Employee Performance at the Karo District Education Office. *Metadata Scientific Journal* 3 (1) : 308 – 321.
- Rahmi, A., Achmad, G. N., & Adhimursandi, D. (2020). The Effect of Leadership and Empowerment Style and Motivation on Work Discipline and Employee 2021. *ALIGNMENT: Journal of Administration and Educational Management* 4(2):130-140
- Siagian, S. P. 2014. *Human Resource Management*. Bumi Aksara, Jakarta.
- Stinglhamber, F., Caesens, G., Chalmagne, B., Demoulin, S., & Maurage, P. (2021). Leader–Member Exchange and Organizational Dehumanization: The Role of Supervisor's Organizational Embodiment. *European Management Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2021.01.006>
- Soejono, S. 2005. *Sociology An Introduction*. Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta.
- Suhudi, N. E., Sunaryo, H., & Priyono, A. A. (2018). The Influence of Work Motivation, Leadership and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance (Office of Babulu District, North Penajam Paser Regency, East Kalimantan). *Scientific Journal of Management Research*, 7(02), 71-80. <http://riset.unisma.ac.id/index.php/jrm/article/view/1042/1071>
- Sutrisno, E. 2009. *Human Resource Management First edition*. Kencana Prenada Media Group, Jakarta.